

1. Samples preparation

As part of the project, a broad spectrum of analytical methods was applied to obtain reliable provenance identification marble samples from different archaeological sites. First, the marble objects were carefully examined macroscopically, taking into consideration its colour, fabric, presence of veins, and grain size. This is particularly important in the case of small samples, for which preparation for analysis further limits the observed area. Subsequently, small flakes were removed from the hidden or damaged areas of all marble items using a chisel. The samples were then divided into two parts. One part was embedded in a cold-setting polyester resin, polished, and used to prepare an uncovered thin section for microscopic analyses under an optical (OM) and cathodoluminescence (CL) microscope, and for selected samples under a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The smaller remaining portion of the sample was mechanically cleaned using a rotary tool equipped with a grit diamond disc and then powdered for the X-ray diffraction (XRD) and isotopic analyses ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$, $\delta^{18}\text{O}$, $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$) using an agate mortar or a rotary tool equipped with sintered diamond microdrills.

2. Minero-petrographic analyses

2.1. Optical microscopy (OM)

Observations were performed on thin sections using a NIKON Eclipse LV100POL microscope under plane- and cross-polarised light at the Institute of Geological Sciences, Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland. NIS-Elements Basic v.3.2 software was used to operate the camera and measure the MGS. The minero-petrographic study aimed to determine the following diagnostic features.

- texture (homeoblastic, i.e. with roughly isodiametric grains, or heteroblastic, i.e. with grains of various dimensions);

- type of fabric (e.g. mosaic, mortar, etc.);
- boundary shapes of calcite/dolomite crystals (e.g. straight, curved, sutured, embayed);
- maximum grain size (MGS);
- semi-quantitative presence of accessory minerals.

For this part of the investigation, the specific studies by Lazzarini et al. (1980), Gorgoni et al. (2002), and Antonelli and Lazzarini (2015) were used as well as a direct comparison between the thin section of each sample and thin sections made of marbles collected in the quarries of Asia Minor within Project Marmora Asiatica (see <http://www.marmoraasiatica.uw.edu.pl>).

2.2. Cathodoluminescence microscopy (CL)

Thin sections were investigated using a CITL Mk5-2 cold cathode stage combined with a Nikon Eclipse 80i polarising microscope at the Institute of Geological Sciences of the Polish Academy of Sciences, Warsaw, Poland. The operating conditions were ~17 kV beam energy and ~0.3 mA beam current at ~0.003 mBar vacuum. The characterised features include the dominant CL colour and its intensity and distribution. The obtained CL patterns were compared to those reported by Barbin et al. (1992), Lapuente and Royo (2016) and Blanc et al. (2020). Additionally, CL observations usually allow the distinction between calcite and dolomite and can be helpful in accessory mineral identification.

2.3. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

In addition, accessory minerals were investigated in thin sections coated with carbon using a ZEISS Sigma VP scanning electron microscope equipped with a Bruker XFlash 6|10 EDS analyser at the Faculty of Geology, University of Warsaw, Poland. The acquired results were compared with the data compiled by Capedri et al. (2004) and Antonelli and Lazzarini (2015).

2.4. X-ray diffractometry (XRD)

Quantitative mineral compositions were identified using an X'Pert PRO MPD X-ray powder diffractometer (PANalytical B.V., The Netherlands) in a Bragg–Brentano system at the Faculty of Geology, University of Warsaw, Poland.

3. Isotopic analyses

3.1. Stable C and O isotopes

Measurements were performed at the Stable Isotope Laboratory at the University of Erlangen-Nürnberg, Germany, with reproducibility better than $\pm 0.1\text{‰}$ for both $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{18}\text{O}$. The results were plotted in reference isotope diagrams for the most common marbles used in antiquity with average maximum grain size < 2 mm and > 2 mm, as proposed by Gorgoni et al. (2002) and updated by Antonelli and Lazzarini (2015) and Wielgosz-Rondolino et al. (2024).

3.2. Sr isotope ratio ($^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$)

The measurements were carried out for all samples from which it was possible to collect a sufficient amount of fresh, powdered material (~ 50 mg), in the Isotope Laboratory at the Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland. Powdered carbonate samples were dissolved in ultrapure 5% acetic acid and leached on a mechanical shaker for 24 h at room temperature. The miniaturised chromatographic technique described by Pin et al. (1994) was applied for Sr separation. Some modifications in the column size and concentration of reagents were introduced by Dopieralska (2003). Sr was loaded with a TaCl_5 activator on a single Re filament and analysed in dynamic collection mode on a Finnigan MAT 261 mass spectrometer. The obtained $^{87}\text{Sr}/^{86}\text{Sr}$ values were compared with data from Brilli et al. (2005), supplemented by Gärtner et al. (2011) and Wielgosz-Rondolino et al. (2024).

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